

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COMPETENCE IN NATURAL GEOGRAPHY

*Shodiyeva Go'zal Raxmatullayevna,
Doctoral student of Samarkand State University*

Abstract. In this article, six pedagogical spheres of developing students' competence in natural geography are presented and the essence of them is revealed.

Key words: competence, pedagogical condition, natural geography, didactic tool, creative thinking

There are many interpretations and definitions of the concept of "pedagogical condition" in the scientific and methodical literature on pedagogy. Its essence is a set of measures aimed at increasing the effectiveness of pedagogical activity [1]. Pedagogical conditions act as a set of factors that enable the achievement of didactic goals [2]. The structure of the complex of pedagogical conditions implies the ability of the pedagogical process to develop by changing the structure of elements and the nature of interaction between them, depending on the changes in the goals and tasks of the pedagogical process [3].

Therefore, it is important to clarify pedagogical conditions in the development of professional competence of students studying in higher education institutions.

Modern geographical education, based on the interconnection of scientific knowledge with the world of human needs, is designed to help prepare graduates of educational institutions of all levels for independent work in various geographical realities. "The world trends that require the modernization of geography education consist of the need to develop new approaches, including pedagogical conditions, in changing the goals and content of its teaching, improving didactic tools, and determining the final result" [4]. The theoretical analyzes carried out in this regard made it possible to determine the necessary pedagogical conditions for the development of professional competence of students, including geographical competence, during the educational process of higher educational institutions:

The first pedagogical condition is self-awareness and orientation to the subjectivity of a person who can express himself. This pedagogical condition is based on modern trends in the development of geographical competence of students, as well as on the leading achievements in the field of pedagogy and psychology.

The second condition is the availability of methodological materials related to natural geography. It serves as the main foundation for students to study topics

related to natural geography, perform practical tasks, conduct various experiments, and prepare projects.

This pedagogical condition is the use of educational environments. Educational environments provide students with all educational and methodological resources. It allows students to independently learn educational information about geography.

The fourth pedagogical condition is a well-developed consultation system between professors and students. This pedagogic condition allows students to face problems that they cannot solve independently while performing various practical assignments related to natural geography and conducting field practice experiments. "They can be related to the organizational part or directly to the topic on which the project is being developed. In such cases, it is necessary to contact the professor-educator who will help to solve the problems and questions that have arisen so that the quality of the performed tasks is not affected" [5]. Also, consultations can perform control functions, which allows the teaching professor to monitor the level of readiness of practical tasks and experimental work, as well as to observe how each student manifests himself and how much he participates in the activities of conducting experiments. It is effective to implement the counseling system using educational environments in online form.

The fifth pedagogical condition is the introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies to the education of geography through experimentation, designed to develop students' competence in natural geography. By applying scientific-based innovative pedagogical technologies to the process of geography education and training, it is possible to conduct effective training of professors and students, to increase students' interest in science, to develop their creative thinking and competence.

The sixth pedagogical requirement is the creation of a creative environment for improving the teaching effectiveness of natural geography and organizing independent education of students.

In short, the development of students' competence in natural geography is achieved by following the pedagogical conditions put forward in the research, increasing the creative potential of the student, developing his interests, abilities, opportunities and subjective position. All of these create the basis for the development of students' competence in natural geography during the educational process of higher educational institutions, as well as the opportunity to master various methods of acquiring new knowledge.

References:

1. Куприянов Б. В., Дынина С. А. Современные подходы к определению сущности категории «Педагогические условия» // Вестник Костромского гос. университета им. Н. А. Некрасова. 2001. – № 2. – С. 101-104.
2. 66. Ипполитова Н.В. Анализ понятия «педагогические условия»: сущность, классификация» / Н.В. Ипполитова, Н.С. Стерхова // General and Professional Education. 2012. – № 1. – С. 11. (С. 8-14.)
3. 19. Баранов А.С. Методика изучения Всемирного наследия с использованием компьютерных технологий в курсе географии 10 класса // Автореферат диссертации на соискание ученой степени кандидата педагогических наук. – Санкт-Петербург, 2005. – 19 с.
4. Сеницын, И. С. Подготовка студентов к использованию статистических методов в профессиональной деятельности учителя географии [Текст] / И. С. Сеницын // Современная система образования : теория и практика [Текст] : монография. Книга 2 / под ред. И. В. Ткаченко – Ставрополь : Логос, 2015. – С. 130–148.
5. Сердюк М.Л. Метод проектов как средство развития творческих способностей учащихся. (На примере образовательной области «Технология»): дис. ... канд. пед. наук. Киров, 2002. – 158 с.